

Assessment of Professional Stress at the Port Autonome de Conakry (PAC) in 2020

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Abstract:-

➤ Introduction

Stress is defined by Lazarus, Folkman (1984) and Stora (2002) as being a psychological state resulting from the perception of an imbalance between the perceived expectations and the self-evaluation of one's own capacities to meet the demands of the task. . objective: to assess the stress among workers at the Autonomous Port of Conakry.

➤ Materials and Methods

This was a prospective study of a descriptive type which lasted six (06) months from 06 Jan 2020 to 06 July 2020. It focused on the workers of the Autonomous Port of Conakry.

➤ Results

Our study focused on 222 employees of the Autonomous Port of Conakry who were all subordinates. In our series, the 41-60 age group was the most represented with 52.25% and the majority of our respondents had a seniority of between 1-15 years or 68.46%. The employees of the Autonomous Port of Conakry who participated in our study were mainly 82.89% men, 45.04% smokers and 12.16% alcoholics. Conclusion: It appears that stress is a very common condition among workers at the Autonomous Port of Conakry. This state is mainly blamed by workers in work-related tasks. Better work organization with a reduction in the workload or an increase in the number of workers would allow better management of stress among these workers.

Keywords:- Stress - Occupation – Port- Workers

List of Abbreviations

ETSA: European Agency for Safety and Health at Work

AIS: American Institute of Stress

ILO: International Labour Office

CHST: Comité d'Hygiène et de la Sécurité au Travail

FEACVT: European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions

INRS: Institut National de Recherche en Sécurité

PAC: Port Autonome de Conakry

FSTS: Faculty of Technical Sciences and Health

I. INTRODUCTION

Stress is defined as a psychological state resulting from the perception of an imbalance between imbalance between perceived expectations and self-assessment of one's own ability to meet the demands of the task[1].

Work is a major source of stress; work overload, physical hazards, time constraints have a direct impact on the quality of work life, health and well-being of the individual [2]. The competitiveness of an autonomous port results from the speed with which ships are handled. The need for speed in unloading ships imposes time constraints that influence occupational health [3,4]. The use of new working methods in the port sector is based on a high degree of mechanisation of activities, exposing employees to occupational risks that may lead to work-related accidents [1].

The International Labour Office (ILO) estimates that stress leads to increased absenteeism due to illness, premature turnover of staff, retirement due to ill health, reduced production and quality, and disputes between employees and their employers[5].

In the United States, according to the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH), the cost of stress is estimated to be around \$200 billion per year for North American companies [6].

In Europe, the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (FEACVT) estimates that 22% of employees are victims of stress; 5% of harassment and 5% of physical violence [7].

In Morocco Chatillon DA et al. reported in their study on stress that 65% of nurses reported being stressed at work [8].

In Cameroon Owana Manga LJ et al. reported in their study on occupational stress among pharmacy workers in Douala that 102 participants were stressed, i.e. 71.80% [9] .

In Senegal, Dia et al. reported in their study on the evaluation of stress among staff in the refugee and asylum seeker service in Dakar that the prevalence of stress was 40.38% [10] .

It is in this context that we initiated this study, the objective of which is to evaluate professional stress among the staff of the Autonomous Port of Conakry (PAC); to describe its manifestations and to propose effective prevention strategies applicable to this work environment

II. METHODOLOGY

Framework of the study: the Autonomous Port of Conakry served as a framework for this study.

Built in 1849 and located on the island of Tombo in the commune of Kaloum, it covers an area of about 20 hectares.

➤ Materials

This study focused on port employees working in the various departments during our study period.

Collection medium: A pre-established survey form was used as a medium.

➤ Methods

- *Type and duration of study*

It was a prospective study of descriptive and analytical type with a duration of six (6) months from 06 January to 06 July 2020.

- *Populations*

Target population: all employees of the Autonomous Port of Conakry during our study period were our target population.

Study population: all permanent and contractual employees present during the study period were our study population.

- *Selection criteria*

Inclusion criteria: we included in our study all workers of the autonomous port present at the time of the survey and who agreed to participate

Non-inclusion criteria: we did not include in our study all workers from the administrative sector as well as those who did not agree to take part in the questionnaire.

- *Study variables:*

Our variables were qualitative and quantitative and included socio-professional data and questionnaires from the Karasek and Siegrist models.

- *Dependent variables: Stress at work*

Independent variables: Gender - Age - Education - Marital status - Occupational category - Sector of activity - Job tenure - Type of employment contract

- *Collection Tool*

A mixed KARASEK and SIERGRIST questionnaire
Duration of data collection: Data collection lasted 6 months, from 6 January to 6 June 2020

Conduct of the survey: the presentation of the study and its interest was carried out 48 hours before the distribution of the questionnaire in each of the departments concerned by the study

- *Operationalisation of the variables*

According to the KARASEK model, psychological demand is high if the score is above 20 and low if the score is below 20 decision latitude is high if its score is higher than 71 and low if its score is lower than 71

Limitations of the study: the mixed questionnaires (KARASEK and SIERGRIST) and the subjectivity of the respondents.

Ethical considerations: no form of pressure was exerted on the staff to participate in this study; the data were collected and processed with strict respect for anonymity

- *Data analysis*

Data entry and analysis was done in epi info version 7 software.

III. RESULTS

Table I: Socio-professional characteristics of the study subjects

VARIABLES	EFFECTIFS N=222	Pourcentage (%)
Age		
	98	44.14
20-40	116	52.25
41-60	8	3.61
≥ 60		
Length of employment		
1-15	152	68.47
16-30	62	27.92
≥ 30	8	3.61

Gender	Ratio : 4.84	
Male	184	82.89
Female	38	17.11
Level of education		
Primary	28	12.61
Secondary	96	43.24
Higher	65	29.28
Not in school	33	14.87
Marital status		
Single	37	16.67
Married	181	81.53
Widowed	4	1.80

Table II: Distribution of employees according to psychological demand

Psychological demand	Number N=222	Percentage (%)
20	125	56.30
≥ 20	97	43.70
Total	222	100

Table III: Distribution of employees according to decision latitude

Decision latitude	Frequency N=222)	Percentage (%)
< 71	80	36.03
≥ 71	142	63.97
TOTAL	222	100

Table IV: Distribution of employees by department according to the Siegrist model

Service	R>1		R≤1		Total
	n	%	n	%	
General Management	7	3.15	15	6.75	22
Transport and Logistics	16	7.20	48	21.62	64
Technical Department	19	8.55	30	13.51	49
Mechanical Department	27	12.17	60	27.02	87
Total	69	31.08	153	68.92	222

IV. DISCUSSION

This was a descriptive cross-sectional study carried out over a period of six months from January 6 to June 6, 2020, on workers at the Autonomous Port of Conakry.

- In our study 27% of the employees were stressed according to the Karasek model. Laraqui O et al [11] in Morocco, in a study on the evaluation of stress in health personnel, reported that 21.7% of participants declared being stressed.
- Légeron P, in a review on occupational stress, stated that among all the psychosocial risks at work, stress appears to be quantitatively the most important, affecting about 22% of European employees [12].
- In our study, the average age of the respondents was 38.95 ± 8.77 and the age group 41 to 60 years was the most stressed with a frequency of 52.25%.
- Moreno Fortes A et al in their series on "Stress at work and complete mental health of employees had found a predominance of the 30-39 age group among Cape Verdean subjects [13].
- Gintrac A, in a study on work-related stress, concluded that it is the 40-54 age group that suffers the most from stress and related manifestations [14].

- In our study tobacco was the most dominant vice with a frequency of 45.04% followed by alcohol with 12.16%.
- Laraqui O et al in Morocco found in their series that 72.6% consumed more than four cups of tea or coffee daily, 21.4% were smokers, 16% drank alcohol [11].
- In our series, 68.46% of the respondents had a job tenure of 1 to 15 years. Suleman Q et al in Pakistan reported that 46.77% of the operators had a job tenure of 01 to 04 years. [15]
- Kploanyi EE et al in Ghana reported that the employees had a maximum work experience of 5 years in 86.8% of the cases. [16]
- High psychological demand, low decision latitude and low social support were the main stressors.
- Kploanyi E et al in Ghana found the following psychosocial stressors in their study: workload (97.9%), responsibility for others (50.6%) [16].
- Conradie M et al in South Africa reported that the main stressors at work were high workload in 66.3% of cases, followed by lack of participation in decision making in 58.10% [17]

V. CONCLUSION

The deterioration of the quality of working life is now a reality faced by both workers in the performance of their duties and by organisations having to manage numerous psychosocial risks.

The main factors incriminated are high work demands, low decision-making autonomy, low social support from the hierarchy and, above all, poor organisation of work within the autonomous port of Conakry.

An alternative in this case would be to review the operating methods of the employees by granting them more flexibility in the conduct and performance of their tasks.

Thus, the revision and lightening of protocols would not only offer more freedom and autonomy to managers but this would also be seen as a sign of confidence in their ability to manage their workload properly.

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